

THERMOELASTIC STRESS ANALYSIS FOR STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF AEROSPACE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The development of thermoelastic stress analysis systems employing compact low-cost thermal detectors provides an important capability for aircraft structural integrity assurance. In aircraft full-scale durability testing it affords a significantly improved basis for validating finite element modelling of complex airframe components, and can be used to rapidly identify and then monitor fatigue hot spots. To date such systems have mostly been applied to metallic aircraft components and on issues relating primarily to fatigue, however with the growing use of composite materials in aircraft there is interest in how these systems can be applied to composite aircraft components. This paper draws on several case studies from coupon level to full-scale airframe fatigue testing to demonstrate that thermal detector based TSA systems can play an important role in evaluating the structural performance of composite aircraft components.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoelastic Stress Analysis (TSA) is an established experimental stress imaging technique that infers bulk stress from radiometric measurements of temperature via the thermoelastic effect; a phenomenon that describes a reversible coupling between dilatational deformation and temperature in solids [1]. The method has been applied to the study of composite materials for well over 30 years but in a limited way and primarily as a research tool. The reasons for this are manifold and varied. One factor is the difficulty in extracting components of stress (or strain) from bulk stress. This is an issue for both metals and composites but is most acute for the latter due to the added complexity of directional material properties and the strong through-thickness heat diffusion induced by inter-laminar stress discontinuity in laminates with multi-directional layup. By contrast, digital image correlation, a better known and more widely used full-field strain measurement technique, yields component field values by default. Another factor is the traditionally high cost of commercial TSA instrumentation which can be traced to a reliance on cryogenically-cooled infrared detectors, a highly sensitive but relatively expensive imaging technology.

Recent developments warrant a re-examination of these issues. Firstly, the affordability and practicality of TSA hardware has improved dramatically. This follows the recent development of thermal detector based TSA systems which are significantly more compact, rugged and affordable. Moreover, such systems produce comparable, and in some circumstances superior, stress-image quality to cooled detectors [2]. The practical implications for TSA are significant and nowhere more so than in the aerospace sector where these small rugged low-cost thermal detectors have enabled TSA to be applied to important aircraft structural integrity problems. In situ stress surveys of structural test airframes are now routine at the Australian Defence Science and Technology (DST) Group, and recently the approach was applied to several F-35 durability test airframes with excellent results [3]. Such surveys have provided unprecedented insights for structural finite element model validation, and other applications in airframe testing are now being explored [4]. The other key development is the emergence of Multiphysics simulation as a widely accessible computational tool. This capability has made it possible to better understand the effect of ply lay-up and loading rate on the thermoelastic response of multi-layered composites.

This paper focuses primarily on the first issue, that of affordability and practicality. Three case studies are presented involving aircraft structural integrity support activities at DST. These are used to illustrate how the use of thermal detectors has enhanced the role TSA can play in evaluating the structural performance of composite aircraft components. The case studies are introduced in order of test complexity starting with a relatively simple coupon test and ending with two full-scale airframe fatigue tests.

2 COUPON LEVEL – ASSESSMENT OF REPAIRS TO LIGHTWEIGHT COMPOSITE AIRCRAFT STRUCTURE

The issue of composite impact vulnerability is particularly acute for military helicopter operation where impact threats are many. In addition to conventional threats like bird strike and tool drop there are uniquely military hazards such as shell-casing ejection and troop embarkation. Bonded repair is often the most efficient approach to restoring strength in the event of impact damage.

Figure 1 Thermoelastic response of a carbon-fibre/Nomex core sandwich coupon with a bonded doubler. Bottom image is an enlarged and annotated view of the response at 10 Hz with labels referring to features discussed in the text (scale is in nominal mK).

Figure 1 left shows a coupon reminiscent of the honeycomb sandwich construction found in the fuselage of a military helicopter currently in service with the Australian Defence Force. The sandwich consists of 15 mm thick Nomex honeycomb core with two carbon-fibre composite face sheets. Each face sheet comprises three sections of skin abutting at the arrowed locations labelled “cut” in the figure. The centre section of skin between the two cuts forms part of the repair and replaces skin damaged by a hypothetical impact. Load transfer across the repair is achieved by means of a composite doubler that extends 15 mm beyond each cut (the so-called overlap length).

The mechanical performance of the repair was examined using an in-house TSA system equipped with a FLIR A615 vanadium oxide microbolometer. Measurements were taken under a constant amplitude (CA) uniaxial cyclic load at 4 different frequencies; 0.5, 2, 5 and 10 Hz. The observations ranged in duration from approximately 3 minutes at 10 Hz to over one hour at 0.5 Hz. Both in-phase (X-component) and quadrature (Y-component) thermoelastic response components are shown. The former relates to the bulk stress distribution and the latter to the conduction-driven response. Adiabatic conditions are preferred for TSA but this generally requires either a high loading frequency or the absence of stress gradients neither of which applied under the test conditions. The closest

approximation in the present situation was achieved at 10 Hz which is confirmed by the uniformly low quadrature response in the Figure (black corresponds to a null response). An enlarged view of this scan, shown at the bottom of the figure, identifies four features of interest (labelled A-D) for discussion in the next paragraph.

Figure 2 Thermoelastic response profile along line A in Figure 1.

Feature A refers to the thermoelastic response profile (X-component) shown in Figure 2. Focusing on the baseline level of the signal (i.e. disregarding the periodic component) the stress in the parent skin is approximately twice that in the doubler, which is consistent with the doubling of skin thickness in the repaired section. The periodic component of the signal corresponds to alternating resin and carbon-fibre rich pockets in the laminate which is a product of the bi-directional satin-weave material used in its manufacture. Feature B is an isopachic curve that notionally bounds the load transfer zone. Load transfer is seen to occur within the overlap length validating the repair design. Interestingly, the curved shape suggests a significant variation in load transfer length across the specimen with load taken up over a shorter distance at the sides of the specimen as compared to the centre, implying the adhesive shear stresses are higher towards the sides. The next feature (C) refers to an area of elevated stress in the doubler (20% above the average stress level according to the thermoelastic signal) which develops at the location of the cut in the skin beneath and extends a distance of about half the specimen width toward the centre of the doubler. This increased stress reflects the sharp drop in stiffness of the parent skin at the cut. The final feature of interest is the dark triangular-shaped area at the bottom left corner of the doubler (D). This area of near-zero load transfer corresponds to an edge disbond created by impacting a hardened steel wedge into the bond-line to create a fracture. Although detecting such a disbond would present little challenge for standard NDI techniques the TSA scan delivers additional insight by also revealing the structural impact or significance of the damage, i.e. its effect on the mechanical performance of the repair. The case study also highlights that adiabatic or even near-adiabatic conditions are not always necessary to obtain valuable insights into structural behaviour. In the case of the corner disbond for example, testing at a much lower frequency of 0.5 Hz (top row in Figure 1) produces an arguably clearer delineation of the disbond due to the increased heat conduction and its selective attenuation of short-scale (high gradient) features.

3 FULL-SCALE TESTING OF AN AIRCRAFT SUBCOMPONENT

The achievement of adiabatic conditions is much easier for small-scale coupons than for full-scale airframe components. A variety of factors in the design of a full scale test rig contribute to the requirement for a compromise in the maximum loading rate. For the rig used to test F/A-18 centre-barrels at DST Group the maximum effective cycling frequency is ~0.14 Hz which is not unusually low for manoeuvre spectrum loading of large airframe structures. At such rates the scope for TSA is

quite limited as a result of signal attenuation and phase shift due to heat diffusion. Fortunately, by restricting peak loads to a fraction of the maximum spectrum load and maintaining a constant amplitude much higher frequencies can be achieved; 1 Hz in the case of the F/A-18 centre-barrel test program. This approach has enabled detailed study of many different aspects of centre-barrel structural performance, including assessment of the effect and performance of repairs and reinforcements. One such study involved a boron-epoxy doubler designed by the Finnish Air Force to extend the fatigue life of a critical section of the lower flange of the rear bulkhead [5].

Figure 3 Clockwise from top left: (i) the location of the three bulkheads that constitute the centre-barrel structure (ii) a centre barrel installed in the test rig at DST, (iii) a close-up of the doubler installed on the lower flange and (iv) the thermoelastic response of the doubler and flange.

The reinforcement in this case was an 8 ply unidirectional boron-epoxy laminate with a cured thickness of approximately 1.05 mm, and was bonded to the flange using FM300-2 film adhesive. Even though relatively thin the use of boron fibre and a unidirectional lay-up yields a relatively high structural stiffness which leads to a significant reduction in flange stress (over 20%) and concomitantly a significant improvement in fatigue life. The unidirectional layup also confers an advantage for TSA as it eliminates inter-laminar stress discontinuity as a potential source of through-thickness heat diffusion. On this point, it is interesting to note the uniformity of response across the tapered end of the doubler where individual plies are exposed.

The thermoelastic response shown in Figure 3 was taken with the microbolometer attached to the airframe using an articulated arm, as shown in the upper right picture (seen below the circled area). The advantage of this approach is that with the camera attached to and moving in sync with the loaded structure the need for motion compensation is eliminated. Because the camera has low mass and is

relatively inexpensive the approach is straightforward to implement and involves a modest and in this case an acceptable financial risk in the event of structural failure of the bulkhead. The response shows no indication of disbonding or damage in the reinforcement which was not unexpected given the early stage of testing at which the scan was taken. Nonetheless, the scan provided useful reassurance of a well bonded and properly functioning doubler. The ends of the doubler experience a relatively low stress (dark shades) whereas mid-doubler the stress is ~6 times higher, reflecting the much higher stresses in the flange at this location. This provides confidence that the doubler is achieving its design objective. Unfortunately, there was no opportunity to conduct regular monitoring of the reinforcement however one would surmise that such an approach would have been effective in detecting any drop-off in performance due to adhesive failure.

4 WIDE-AREA SCAN OF AN F/A-18A/B OUTER WING SKIN

The F/A-18A/B Hornet Outer Wing Static Testing (HOWSAT) Program is the DST component static test program being used to substantiate fail-safe assumptions about the outer wing leading to a safe-life lifing basis. The basis of the HOWSAT program is to introduce significant damage into the internal metallic structure of the outer wing and ensure the structure can maintain static loads of 120% DLL. One part of this program involved assessing the effect of composite damage on the residual strength of the internally damaged outer wing. A trial of TSA was undertaken to determine if it could be used to identify areas of high stress within the skin under one simple load case to inform critical location selection.

Figure 4 shows the F/A-18 outer wing installed in the HOWSAT structural test rig which is designed to apply representative static wing bending and torsional loads. Pictured is the upper wing surface which is approximately 1.6 m x 1.2 m in size. This entire structure was imaged in a single view by a microbolometer suspended ~4 m above the wing via a pre-existing crane. The thermoelastic response was measured under a CA load sequence with the peak-to-peak load amplitude set to 40% design limit load¹. Since the rig was designed for static testing the cyclic frequency was limited to 0.36 Hz significantly below the rate preferred for TSA of this type of structure given its complex non unidirectional lay-up and the likelihood of this promoting strong through-thickness heat flow.

¹ Due to the test rig being designed to apply only static loading the cyclic loading applied for TSA purposes was not sufficiently controlled to ensure pure CA bending, thus some torsional loads may also have been induced.

Figure 4 Pictured (top left) is an F/A-18 outer wing installed in a loading rig with (top right) a microbolometer suspended 4 m above the wing from a crane hook. Below is the X-component thermoelastic response (scale is nominally in K).

Figure 4 shows the X-component thermoelastic response of the wing skin. The large signal variations within and across the riveted sections in both the span and chord-wise directions appear incongruous with simple wing bending. The complex lay-up, variations in skin thickness, myriad fastened sections with unknown fit-up stresses, a non-adiabatic loading rate and a metallic substructure containing a large number of fatigue cracks induced as part of the damage tolerance study are all factors to consider in interpreting this response. Further, the known latency in the response of one of the main actuators is thought to have introduced a torsional loading component which suggests that at least some of the chord-wise variation is attributable to motion effects. The same would apply in the span-wise direction with respect to the bending load component.

The result is preliminary and more investigation is required to determine the origins of the salient features in the response. The purpose of including this case however was not to speculate on possible explanations but to simply underscore that this type of full-scale composite inspection is viable with low-cost microbolometer systems and could have the potential to furnish useful insights particularly if combined with coupled modelling capabilities that can account for cross-ply interactions at non-adiabatic loading frequencies.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The development of compact low-cost thermoelastic stress analysis instrumentation affords increased opportunity to apply TSA to the structural evaluation of composites. This paper has used case studies in simple coupon testing and full-scale airframe fatigue test programs to underscore the engineering value of thermoelastic response measurements and to demonstrate how these new compact low-cost systems can facilitate the application of TSA to large scale airframe testing.

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